

A phraseological view to AI-powered writing assistant ChatGPT: A corpus-based study

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Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have opened doors for developing novel writing tools that enhance and create innovative ways to assist writers and learners during and after their writing process. Specifically, it can provide immediate and customized feedback and stimulate learners' interests and motivation (Huang et al., 2022; Kuhail et al., 2023). Studies in modern corpus linguistics have demonstrated that language is highly patterned and primarily comprises fixed or semi-fixed units (e.g., Biber, 2009; Hoey, 2005; Sinclair, 1991; Roemer, 2009) that serve critical discourse functions (Tan & Roemer, 2022). Therefore, this study intends to investigate ChatGPT's reliability by analyzing the ChatGPT- edited essays and comparing it with expert editors from a phraseological view.

The L2 learner essays in this study were extracted from the Edited Essays module from the International Corpus Network of Learners of English (ICNALE) (Ishikawa, 2018). Learner essays (n=140) and their fully edited versions (n=140) were selected for this study. Similarly, to test the reliability of ChatGPT in editing learner essays and determining if the process is consistent with human editors, ChatGPT was prompted using the same rubric and required to generate the fully edited versions (n=140) of the 140 original learner essays at once using ChatGPT API. The 3, 4, and 5 phrase-frames were identified based on the established frequency and range thresholds using AntGram (Anthony, 2019) and were manually filtered for meaningfulness. The variability and predictability in the filtered phrase-frames were analyzed, and functional analysis was further conducted. Tentative results indicate that ChatGPT contributes to more variable ($p < 0.001$) and less predictable ($p < 0.001$) 3 phrase-frames but does not show significant differences in frequency. This study could provide insight into the reliability of ChatGPT in editing essays in L2 writing by investigating its capacities. It could also raise awareness of the potential of AI-powered writing assistants in facilitating L2 writing from a phraseological perspective.